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The Aesthetic Functionality of Theatre Costumes in Dance Performances: A Study of the 2016 Imo State Carnival

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Abstract

Costume is one vital element of the theatre that if not given proper consideration can mar the primary idea of a creative piece. Therefore, a theatre costume must serve a theatrical role in its entirety. Carnival performances are artistically rich expressions that rely heavily on costumes not only for beauty, but also for their narrative qualities, movement facilitation and symbolic communication. The creation process of a choreographic piece is one that requires various considerations which costumes are a major part of. This research work focuses on the aesthetic value costumes place on the execution of dances in the 2016 Imo state carnival themed "Imo my Pride Carnival 2016" with the slogan "Ain't Seen Nothing Yet", taking an analytic insight on the ease and comfort of the dancers, interpretative ability of the costumes, performance technique, conceptualization and thematic clarity of the various costumes. The paper also examines the interplay between fabric choice, colour symbolism and the dynamic needs of dance movements. Adopting Roland Barthes' Semiotic Theory and Susanne Langer's Theory of Symbolic forms and Expression Theory of Art as a guide, this work employs the qualitative method of research comprising video analysis, photographic documentation, literature review, information gotten from interviews of costume designers,

dancers, and audience members of the 2016 Imo Sate Carnival. The findings establish that costumes in such cultural performances are not mere adornments but functional tools that bridge the visual and performative elements of dance, contributing significantly to the overall spectacle and message of the performance.

Keywords: Aesthetics, Costume, Choreographic, Conceptualization, Performative

Introduction

Choreography is a creative way of designing, arranging and joining movement phrases for different bodies to form a complete routine. The weight, shape, space, time and flow are factors that should be considered during the creation process as they contribute to a large extent, the outcome of a choreographed piece. The rehearsal process is seen as the testing ground for every effectual element that will be infused to aid the execution of a dance piece. At this stage all factors are put into consideration to see to the easy flow of a dance routine. Costume is one major determinant of the aesthetic makeup of a dance performance and this is as a result of its appeal and functionality. A dancer's costume gives detailed information of the style of dance that is being executed. This information elucidates the historical, occupational, cultural and social makeup of a dance piece.

The inclusion of special clothing in a given performance helps differentiate between a rehearsal and an actual presentation. Even though audience perception of a dance performance is subjective, the costumes help to interpret the choreographer's original idea through the chosen colours and designs which the costume designer has created. The fabrics used to produce these costumes are also important and are determined by the style of dance. Some costumes are created with thick and heavy fabrics while other are made with stretchy, light weight and soft fabrics. The costume designer has to make sure that the costumes are skin friendly and also put in mind the flexibility of the costumes during the production process, as this will add beauty to the movements, thereby heightening the visual pleasure of the audience and at the same time, help the dancers move freely in them.

Statement of the Problem

Carnivals in Nigeria are increasingly celebrated as vibrant displays of culture, music, dance, and art. While much attention has been given to musical acts, dance, and general entertainment, the critical role of costume in shaping the aesthetic and communicative essence of carnival

performances, particularly in the case of the Imo Carnival remains under-explored. A preliminary observation of carnival performances, both live and through media, reveals that costumes serve as the first point of visual engagement for the audience. They are powerful semiotic tools that convey cultural identity, interpret dance themes, and reinforce the overall narrative of a performance. Yet, many carnival performances suffer a disconnect between costume design and thematic intention. In several cases, performers wear costumes that lack symbolic alignment with the central message, resulting in a diluted or misinterpreted performance. Therefore, carnival themes that should find their strong voice in the display of appropriate costumes are weathered down or completely lost.

Despite their visual prominence, carnival costumes often receive minimal attention in planning and scholarship. This is especially true for the Imo Carnival, which remains under-researched in comparison to more popular events like the Calabar or Lagos carnivals. Costume designers face challenges such as insufficient budgets, time constraints, and limited collaboration with choreographers, which compromise the aesthetic and cultural quality of their output. Carnival organizers tend to invest heavily in music, comedy, and stage design, while underestimating the narrative and symbolic power embedded in costume. The result is a recurring thematic derailment in carnival performances, where costume choices fail to support the message or the historical and cultural context intended by the choreographers and performers.

This research, therefore, addresses the gap by critically exploring the role and impact of costume in Imo Carnival performances. It examines how costumes contribute to, enhance, or distort the thematic and symbolic essence of carnival dance, and how they can be optimized as tools for cultural expression and performance coherence.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to examine the aesthetic and symbolic functions of costume in carnival dance performances, with a specific focus on how costume contributes to the thematic expression, visual appeal, and cultural identity in the 2016 Imo Carnival. The objectives are

1. To explore the relationship between costume design and choreographic meaning in the 2016 Imo carnival dance performances.

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2. To analyze how costume contributes to the aesthetic experience and visual symbolism of the Imo Carnival.
 3. To identify the cultural, historical, and thematic messages embedded in the carnival costumes.
 4. To examine the extent to which costume enhances or distorts the intended message of carnival performances.
 5. To evaluate the challenges and limitations faced by costume designers in aligning designs with the central theme of the Imo Carnival.

Research Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research approach, utilizing both descriptive and interpretive strategies to investigate the aesthetic and symbolic significance of costumes in the Imo Carnival. The 2016 Imo Carnival serving as the focal point for examining how costumes function within Nigerian carnival performances.

Data collection techniques will include:

- **Observation** of recorded performances to assess the contextual use and visual impact of costumes.
- **Interviews** with key stakeholders such as costume designers, choreographers, dancers and some audience members to gather perspectives on costume creation, thematic alignment, and cultural symbolism.
- **Photographic and video documentation** to aid in detailed visual analysis of costume features and their interaction with performance.
- **Review of relevant documents**, including festival brochures, costume concept sketches, and existing literature on carnival culture and performance aesthetics in Nigeria.

The data gathered will be subjected to thematic analysis, guided by Langer's theory of symbolic forms and Barthes' semiotic framework, to interpret the communicative and expressive functions of costume within the performance environment.

Theoretical Framework

Roland Barthes' Semiotics Theory

This school of thought interprets costume as a system of signs that interconnects meaning to the audience. The colours, fabrics, and designs of carnival costumes convey information about identity, culture, and

narrative, which are decoded by viewers during performances. Barthes posits that “the photographic image...is a message without a code; from which proposition an important corollary must be immediately drawn: the photographic message is a continuous message.” (Barthes, 1977). His belief suggests that once the spectators view the costumes, meaning is decoded and it is unending. This goes to prove that in as much as the audience perception of costumes can be subjective, there is no costume without a message. He goes further to say “thanks to its code of connotation, the reading of the photograph is thus always historical; it depends on the reader’s ‘knowledge’ just as though it were a matter of real language, intelligible only if one has learned the signs.” (Barthes, 1977). Barthes philosophy sheds more light on the audience perception of costumes, which is the major end result of aesthetics. Costumes in dance performances and carnivals as in this case, are produced based on cultural and historical codes. The audience are able to decode the costumes based on their cultural intimations, elevating the performances’ narrative.

“Every sign supposes a code... ‘Every sign is a signifier – signified – sign’ in a tri-dimensional structure.” (Barthes, 1977). Barthes sets the foundational model of semiotics: the signifier (visual), the signified (conception), and the sign (the message). For example, a headgear painted red (signifier) may signify passion (signified) within the performance. The relationship between the headgear and passion (which could be represented through elements such lines, space, shape or colour in this case becomes the sign that is decoded by the audience. He informs us that “visual mediums are perceived as portraying reality while in fact they are constructing it.” (Barthes, 1977). As simple and easy as costumes may seem, they build social, cultural and thematic concepts that shape audience perception of a performance.

Susanne Langer’s Theory of Symbolic forms and Expression Theory of Art:

This study is grounded in Susan Langer’s Theory of Symbolic forms, which presents art as a form of non-discursive expression that interprets complex emotions and experiences. According to Langer (1953), “art is the creation of forms symbolic of human feeling”. In carnivals and other dance performances, these symbols are created through the elements which include space, movement, time, energy, each exemplifying meaning. Within this broader framework lies Langer’s Expression Theory of Art, which tells us that art does not only show emotions but also gives meaning to feelings. She says that “the artist’s job is not to feel, but to create a form in which

feeling can be communicated.” Langer’s view explains that the performer is a vehicle through which expressions rather than emotions are conveyed to the audience. Costumes when integrated into dance performances, go beyond beautification and functionality. They become an extension of the dancer’s body, transforming movements and emotions into visual form, which enhances the emotive experience of the performance.

Literature Review

In a dance performance, costume plays a vital role in communicating the underlying idea of a dance piece to its audience. The texture, style and colour contribute a great deal to the execution of the dance piece. At the first glance of a costume on the body of the performer, the historical, social, cultural, occupational and geographical meaning is established even before the performance commences. The costumes create a sense of belonging for the audience and increases their ability to relate with the dance that is being performed.

For a dance performance, little can be said about the fluidity of movements on the part of the dancers if reasonable consideration is not given to the dexterity the costumes play in relation to the dance movement. Therefore, a costumier must work closely with the choreographer in order to understand his/her creative ideas, dance patterns and floor movements so as to come up with costumes that complement the dance in style, colour, comfort, fluidity and idea interpretation.

Carnivals are socio-cultural spectacles rooted in communal expression, identity, and celebration. Scholars such as Falassi (1987) argues that carnivals operate as ritualistic performances that bring together music, dance, costume, and social commentary. In Nigeria, major carnivals such as Calabar and Lagos have received attention for their economic, political, and cultural significance, but the Imo Carnival remains under-examined in academic discourse. Existing literature often emphasizes entertainment value and tourism, neglecting the deep symbolic layers embedded in the visual components of performance. A very significant aspect of a carnival is the aesthetics portrayed by carefully crafted costumes worn by the participants in the different dance trains. The role of costumes in a carnival train and dance cannot be overemphasized, thus making it a vital part of the carnival.

Costume is more than attire; it is a visual language that conveys character, status, emotion, and theme. Monks (2010), explores how costume performs a central role in theatrical meaning-making, shaping audience interpretation and embodying character identity. In the context of carnival, where performance is public and spectacular, costume becomes a primary visual cue that sets the tone for audience interpretation. Scholars such as Adshead-Lansdale and Layson (1994) emphasize that costume and choreography must be designed in tandem to ensure coherence between visual and kinesthetic expression.

In carnival dance, costumes contribute to rhythm, color dynamics, and symbolic meaning. When used effectively, they enhance the flow of movement and deepen the audience's engagement with the performance.

Costume and Performer Experience

Some studies directly explore how costume affects dancer comfort, mobility, and emotional expression. Scholars such as Dils and Albright (2001) have noted that bodily experience and physical environment, including costume, directly impact performance quality. Discomfort caused by poorly designed costumes can restrict movement and dilute expressiveness, whereas well-considered designs enhance both physical ease and emotional connection with the role. This aspect is essential to carnival dance, which often demands extended physical exertion in open-air conditions, requiring costumes that balance aesthetics with practicality. Costume designers must therefore consider materials, climate, body types, and choreographic demands in the production process.

Costumes are not merely visual enhancements but are vital components of performance meaning-making. Through the lenses of semiotics and symbolic theory, the literature provides tools for analyzing how costume communicates culture, emotion, and narrative. The review also identifies key gaps in scholarship that justify the present study. The next chapter outlines the methodology employed to explore these themes within the context of the Imo Carnival.

A Brief History of the Imo State Carnival

The Imo carnival is one of the foremost carnivals in Nigeria tagged the "celebration of unity" as its main purpose is to promote the unanimity of all the festivals held in the state. The carnival was created as part of the vision

to make the culture of Imo state appreciated by Nigerians and the world at large. The carnival however, has been designed to be an annual event which commences on the 16th of December and lasts till the 31st of December. The yearly event has boosted the cultural mosaic of Nigeria in the process of entertaining millions of spectators/tourists within and outside the domain of the state. This helps to boost the tourism industry for all stakeholders. The carnival has boosted the cultural mosaic of Nigeria by entertaining millions of spectators/tourists within and outside the domain of the state. This helps to boost the tourism industry for all stakeholders. Notably, Buchi George, the initiator and the founder of the carnival is also the executive director of the Imo Carnival Development Commission.

The carnival was held for the first time in the year 2011, adopting the name, Imo carnival. It envisions to celebrate the unity of all the festivals in the state (GoWhereWhen, n.d.). Imo state carnival presents a platform for brand visibility for consumer and market awareness. It promotes cultural heritage, unite Nigerians despite the ethnic diversity and at the same time strengthen the capacity of locals to participate in the carnival in terms of economic benefits. The carnival employs different performances to boost the aesthetics of the event. These include, Ahianjoku festival, Ozunimo festival, Mmanwu, fashion shows, traditional wrestling, Okorochoa dance, traditional dances, beauty pageants, Mr. and Miss Tourism Imo being the top beauty pageant held and a massive street parade, Igbo Poetry and talk show, masquerade band, traditional and contemporary musical performance. The carnival also creates an avenue for all traditional rulers and members of the royal cabinet to be part of the celebration.

Findings

The findings of the study were gathered from data that was collected through interviews, observations, document reviews, and visual analysis of costumes used in the 2016 Imo Carnival themed “Imo my Pride” with the slogan “Ain’t Seen Nothing Yet”. The thematic analysis yielded the following findings:

Relationship between Costume Design and Choreographic Meaning

The costume design was found to be closely tied to the choreographic intent in Imo Carnival performances. Designers and choreographers collaborated to ensure that costume features such as flexibility, colour contrast, and

fabric movement supported the dance's rhythm and energy. For example, lightweight, stretchable fabrics were preferred for routines with fast-paced choreography, while heavier materials were used for more regal, symbolic portrayals. Participants agreed that costume choices often influenced the development of movement and helped communicate the dancer's role more effectively.

Contribution of Costume to Aesthetic Experience and Visual Symbolism

Costumes were described as the most visually captivating aspect of the Imo Carnival. They played a key role in enhancing the audience's experience by creating spectacle, representing local identity, and attracting media attention. Colours, symbols, and exaggeration in costume designs contributed significantly to visual storytelling. Interviewees emphasized that without compelling costumes, the carnival would lose its vibrancy and cultural magnetism.

Cultural, Historical, and Thematic Messages in Carnival Costumes

The study reveals that costume designers embedded significant cultural and historical meanings into their work. Costumes referenced the Nigerian heritage, folklore, traditional occupations, and community struggles. For instance, the Deputy Governor's band were dressed in costumes inspired by Igbo masquerades with stilt walkers, while others used designs to tell stories of colonial resistance or environmental issues. Costumes such as sports wears and graduation gowns could also be seen on participants to symbolize the theme "Imo my Pride" and to showcase the state's love for sports and education. However, a few costumes appeared generic, lacking cultural symbols or alignment with the carnival's theme, due to time pressure or limited cultural research.

Costume as a Tool for Enhancing or Distorting Performance Themes

While costumes often help clarify a performance's intent, the study found several instances where poor costume choices weakened the message. For example, some bands interpreting a traditional concept wore modern, glittery fabrics that clashed with the narrative. Such mismatches caused confusion among spectators and critics. Overall, participants agreed that when costumes were well-aligned with the storyline, they deepened audience engagement and understanding.

Challenges Faced by Costume Designers in Theme Alignment

Designers reported multiple constraints affecting their work. These included tight budgets, time constraints, and lack of skilled artisans. Many expressed concerns about the dominance of Western fashion influences that overshadowed indigenous creativity. Others mentioned limited access to culturally appropriate materials, which affected authenticity. Despite these challenges, most designers remained committed to preserving cultural integrity through their work.

The Deputy Governor's Band, Imo State Carnival 2016

Dance costumes and Train, Imo Carnival 2016

Dance costumes and Train, Imo Carnival 2016

Imo House of Assembly Band in their Dance Costumes

Dance costumes, Imo Carnival 2016

Dance costumes and Train, Imo Carnival 2016

Costumes with Graduation Caps Showing Imo State's love for Education

Mr and Miss Imo Carnival 2016 Pageant

Mr and Miss Imo Carnival 2016 Pageant

Discussion of Findings

Costume as an Extension of Choreographic Intent

The findings affirm that costume design is not a separate element from choreography, but an integral part of it. This is consistent with Susanne Langer's theory of symbolic forms, which suggests that artistic elements express patterns of feeling and internal experience. The study found that some of the costumes were consciously designed to complement specific movement styles and rhythms. Lightweight and stretchable materials were used to facilitate fluid movement, while elaborate and heavier costumes were assigned to dancers playing regal or symbolic roles. This aligns with Langer's view that art objectifies subjective feeling, and costumes in dance do this visually through form, texture, and motion. The relationship between body and costume, therefore, is a dynamic interaction where the costume influences not only how the dancer appears but how the dancer moves.

Designers and choreographers collaborated to ensure that costume features such as flexibility, colour contrast, and fabric movement supported the dance's rhythm and energy. For example, lightweight, stretchable fabrics were preferred for routines with fast-paced choreography, while heavier materials were used for more regal, symbolic portrayals. Participants agreed that costume choices often influenced the development of movement phrases and helped communicate the dancer's role more effectively. While dancer comfort and mobility were central concerns in the findings, some dancers in other bands expressed discomfort with costumes that were too tight, too heavy, or made of materials that caused irritation. These physical constraints not only limited their range of motion but also detracted from the emotional expressiveness and technical delivery of the performance. On the other hand, when costumes were designed with dancer input factoring in heat, stretch, fit, and weight, performers reported a sense of confidence, freedom, and enhanced embodiment of their characters. Thus, the functional relationship between costume design and dancer comfort is crucial for achieving a fluid and emotionally resonant performance.

Costumes and the Aesthetic Experience of Carnival

Costumes were consistently identified as central to the visual and emotional impact of the Imo Carnival. Participants emphasized that before any

choreography begins, the audience's first impression is shaped by what the performers wear. This underscores Barthes' (1977) notion that visual elements operate as systems of signification: they speak before the performers do. The costume acts as a "continuous message" (Barthes, 1977), setting the tone for the audience's emotional and interpretive experience. Whether adorned with cultural symbols, feathers, or elaborate headpieces, carnival costumes offer a non-verbal language that communicates mood, cultural identity, and status. This also supports Langer's view that art, especially performance, is a symbolic form that communicates human feeling without the use of discursive language.

Cultural, Historical, and Thematic Interpretation through Costume

A significant finding of the study was the use of costume to convey cultural and historical messages. Designs reflected Igbo heritage, referencing local legends, occupations, and traditional aesthetics. In line with Barthes' semiotic theory, these costumes functioned as signs, where specific elements (e.g., uli patterns, animal symbols, masquerade costumes and masks) were signifiers pointing to deeper cultural signified.

Costume, in this context, becomes a cultural text to be read by an informed audience. As Barthes (1977) explains, the reading of visual signs depends on the viewer's cultural knowledge, making costumes both inclusive and exclusive communicative tools. When these cultural signs are absent or unclear, the audience's understanding and engagement can be weakened.

Costumes as Clarifiers or Distorters of Meaning

While costumes often serve to enhance thematic understanding, the study reveals that inappropriate costume choices sometimes disrupted the clarity of the carnival performance's message. When modern or misaligned costume elements are introduced into a traditional narrative without contextual justification, they create a semiotic rupture that confuses the audience. This highlights the need for costume designers and choreographers to work collaboratively with cultural consultants and researchers to maintain thematic integrity.

Challenges Faced by Costume Designers

Designers expressed numerous constraints that hindered the creation of effective and culturally relevant costumes. These include limited funding,

lack of skilled labor, time constraints, and pressure to conform to global fashion trends. Such challenges often lead to the use of generic or recycled costume ideas that weaken the authenticity and symbolic strength of performances.

This study has demonstrated that costume is a fundamental component of carnival dance performance. It goes beyond decoration or visual appeal to function as a powerful tool of symbolic communication and artistic expression. When designed with intention and cultural awareness, costumes enhance the narrative, emotional, and visual elements of the performance, deepening audience engagement and reinforcing thematic cohesion.

The Imo Carnival, as a case study, revealed how costumes reflect cultural identity, embody tradition, and translate abstract themes into visible, moving forms. However, the research also exposes key gaps and challenges, such as lack of funding, thematic inconsistency, and weak costume-choreography alignment. These issues not only affect the quality of the performance but also hinder the preservation and promotion of cultural values through costume.

In essence, the role of costume in the Imo Carnival illustrates how visual design, cultural narrative, and performance merge to form a complex semiotic experience that is both entertaining and educational. Ensuring that costume design is given its rightful importance in planning and execution is therefore critical to the future of Nigerian carnival performances and cultural preservation.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that costume is a fundamental component of carnival dance performance. It goes beyond decoration or visual appeal to function as a powerful tool of symbolic communication and artistic expression. When designed with intention and cultural awareness, costumes enhance the narrative, emotional, and visual elements of the performance, deepening audience engagement and reinforcing thematic cohesion. The Imo Carnival, as a case study, reveals how costumes reflect cultural identity, embody tradition, and translate abstract themes into visible, moving forms. However, the research also exposed key gaps and challenges, such as lack of funding, thematic inconsistency, and weak costume-choreography alignment. These issues not only affect the quality of

the performance but also hinder the preservation and promotion of cultural values through costume.

From a theoretical standpoint, the findings align with Susanne Langer's notion that art symbolizes felt life and with Roland Barthes' view that visual elements convey layered meanings through systems of signs. Together, these frameworks support the conclusion that costume design in carnival dance should be treated as a central artistic and communicative process, rather than a secondary or decorative one. In essence, the role of costume in the Imo Carnival illustrates how visual design, cultural narrative, and performance merge to form a complex semiotic experience that is both entertaining and educational. Ensuring that costume design is given its rightful importance in planning and execution is therefore critical to the future of Nigerian carnival performances and cultural preservation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations will help cover the gaps in the costume department of the Imo Carnival and improve the costuming of subsequent ones:

1. ***Strengthen Collaboration Between Choreographers and Costume Designers:*** To ensure thematic and symbolic alignment, performance teams should develop costumes in close consultation with choreographers and cultural advisors.
2. ***Provide Training and Capacity Building for Costume Designers:*** Government agencies, private sponsors, and cultural institutions should organize workshops and funding schemes to enhance the creative skills and cultural literacy of designers.
3. ***Integrate Cultural Research into the Design Process:*** Costume designs should be grounded in accurate cultural and historical research to enhance authenticity and audience connection.
4. ***Increase Budget Allocation for Costume Production:*** To avoid symbolic disconnection due to poor quality or last-minute improvisation, carnival organizers should prioritize funding for costume development.
5. ***Develop Guidelines for Thematic Consistency:*** Carnival committees should provide clear costume themes and expectations early in the planning process, ensuring each troupe aligns with the overall narrative of the carnival.

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6. *Encourage Documentation and Archiving of Costume Designs:* Establishing a visual and textual archive of past carnival costumes would support future designers and researchers in preserving and evolving the cultural identity of the Imo Carnival.

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